

Predisposing Determinants as Correlates of the Use of Midday Meal Scheme in Public Secondary Schools' Nutrition Needs in Delta State

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Abstract

The Midday Meal Scheme is a globally recognized school meal program aimed at addressing classroom hunger and improving student health. This study adopted a descriptive survey research design to examine the predisposing determinants influencing the utilization of the Midday Meal Scheme in public secondary schools in Delta State. A sample of 300 students was purposively selected from ten randomly chosen public secondary schools in Ethiope West Local Government Area who are the direct beneficiaries of the Midday Meal Scheme. Data was collected using a self-developed questionnaire based on a modified four-point Likert scale, with Cronbach's Alpha reliability coefficient of 0.68. Ethical considerations were strictly followed, including informed consent, confidentiality, and approval from school authorities and the Delta State Ministry of Education. Findings revealed that the scheme significantly reduced student poverty ($\chi^2 = 82.00$), although government funding was insufficient despite policy support ($\chi^2 = 62.50$). Additionally, the scheme contributed to increased school enrollment ($\chi^2 = 110.50$). These results highlight the critical role of the Midday Meal Scheme in enhancing students' welfare and access to education. To maximize its benefits, sustained funding, policy implementation, and government support are essential for ensuring long-term program success and effectiveness.

Keywords: Midday Meal Scheme, School Feeding Programs, Poverty Alleviation and Food Security.

Introduction

The Midday Meal Scheme (MDM) is a well-established school meal program implemented across various countries, providing free lunches to students on school days. The program aims to tackle classroom hunger, enhance school enrollment and attendance, promote social interactions among students, combat malnutrition, and create job opportunities for women. Integrating nutritional support into school education is a key approach to achieving free and compulsory Universal Basic Education of acceptable quality for all students in public secondary schools in Delta State. The Midday Meal Programme is one such initiative that plays a crucial role in improving students' nutritional intake.

For over five decades, the MDM program has been in operation to enhance the nutritional well-being of economically disadvantaged children and to increase school enrollment (Gopalan, 2003). However, logistical and financial constraints have hindered its consistent implementation in many areas, except for a few successful cases. Proper nutrition is vital for good health, and consuming a well-balanced diet is especially

important during childhood and adolescence, as it supports growth, energy levels, academic performance, participation in school sports, and other activities (Igbunu & Idehen, 2007). The scheme is designed to address "classroom hunger" by ensuring that students receive nutritious meals during school hours.

Research has highlighted several advantages of the MDM program, including increased student enrollment, higher attendance and retention rates, reduced dropout rates, and improved academic outcomes (Chakraborty & Jayaraman, 2019; Raveenthiranathan et al., 2024; World Food Programme (WFP), 2019). Additionally, the program fosters social inclusion and provides employment opportunities for women in rural areas. However, food safety concerns have been raised due to reported cases of foodborne illnesses resulting from contaminated street food, which pose health risks to students.

The MDM scheme is structured to supply approximately one-third of a child's daily nutritional needs through a freshly prepared hot meal (Anuradha, 2022). Some critics argue that for children from low-income families, the school meal might act as a substitute rather than a supplement to home-cooked meals. A study by Paul et al. (2021) in West Bengal examined the impact of MDM on student academic performance, concluding that the initiative had a significantly positive effect on learning outcomes based on Chi-square test findings. Similarly, Chisala (2017) emphasized that poverty and hunger not only undermine children's health and development but also negatively affect their ability to learn and attend school regularly.

While some consider MDM a populist initiative designed as a broad welfare program (Nagaraju, 2014), research suggests that its success is primarily driven by dedicated public leaders and institutions. Job (2024) explored the role of policymakers in the evolution of the Midday Meal Policy and found that its effectiveness is supported by contributions from religious organizations, non-governmental organizations (NGOs), local government bodies, Parliament, the Supreme Court, and officials at various levels of governance.

A study by Paltasingh (2014) assessed government interventions through the MDM scheme, examining program inspections in Mehsana and Sabarkantha. The findings indicated inconsistencies in monitoring, with some schools going an entire year without inspections, while others underwent monthly, biannual, or occasional evaluations. Meanwhile, Mirakjar and Narayanswamy (2019) analyzed the program's impact on student enrollment and dropout rates in rural government schools. Their study revealed that most parents had only primary or upper primary education, were engaged in agriculture, and had an annual income below Rs. 50,000. Although the program contributed to reducing dropout rates, a decline in school enrollment was observed between 2011–12 and 2014–15.

Beyond improving enrollment and retention, the MDM scheme has played a critical role in enhancing students' nutritional status, allowing disadvantaged children to attend school consistently and actively engage in academic activities (Kadari & Roy, 2016).

Secondary education is the education children receive after primary education and before the tertiary stage. The age group of people receiving secondary education falls between 12 to 17 years plus (Geulayov et al., 2024). According to Delta State Ministry of Basic and Secondary Education (2024), there were 495 Post Primary Schools in Delta State. From this Household Survey (2003), the enrollment of public post primary education age group showed that out of 9639 sampled population considered 7456 were found to be in school enrollment representing about 77%. The reason for the Increase in the school enrollment can be attributed to the encouragement of girl-child education as well as quest from people to acquire education for better living in the society. The Midday Meal Scheme (MDM) serves as a vital intervention to improve students' nutritional status, enhance school attendance, and boost academic performance. However, its effectiveness is influenced by several predisposing determinants that impact students' willingness and ability to utilize the program. Despite the benefits to be enjoyed, many students in public secondary schools in Delta State might still not fully participate in the scheme due to socioeconomic, institutional, and cultural factors. Numerous researchers (Dreze and Goyal, 2003; Afridi, 2010; Afridi et al., 2010; Afridi, 2011; Afridi et al., 2013; Singh et al., 2014; Jayaraman and Simroth, 2015) showed that the impact of MDM included improve their ability to concentrate and learn in class, the retention of students, better academic outcomes, fostering social cohesion in schools, improved attendance and learning outcomes and improved health status.

There has been shift from the emphasis on schools to employ workers and cooks to prepare and coordinate school meal to the employment of services of food vendors, hawkers who prepare the food from their home and bring them to the schools. Due to some logistics, bureaucratic and financial problems, this scheme has suffered a lot of setbacks in most states in Nigeria. Poor feeding predisposes school children to many health problems. School meal is an aspect of school nutrition programme organized within the school health services. Titus (2018) stated that most school children do not eat balanced diet due to some constrains as poverty and ignorant on the part of the parents, non-involvement of the government, growth in school enrollment. Mordi (2010) observed that it is not only the availability of food and money to buy it alone that affects the nutritional status of students but other factors as socio-economic factor, family size and political factors. Most public secondary schools in this state do not have midday meal (MDM) scheme in their school programme except few boarding schools. In most cases, most students are being seen carrying their personal food or going across the ever busy roads to buy foods from the vendors, whose foods the teachers have no access for inspection. If the food is ether prepared by hired cooks or accredited food vendor, the food will be exposed for daily check by the assigned teachers before the students are permitted to consume the food.

Building on this foundation, the researchers seek to explore the key factors influencing the utilization of the Midday Meal Scheme in public secondary schools in Delta State. The study aims to: assess the impact of the Midday Meal Scheme on the poverty levels of students in public secondary schools in Delta State; evaluate the extent of State Government involvement in the scheme's implementation; and analyze the scheme's effect on school enrollment rates.

The research is guided by the following hypotheses:

1. There is no significant correlation between students' poverty levels and the Midday Meal Scheme in public secondary schools in Delta State.
2. There is no significant correlation between the lack of State Government involvement and the implementation of the Midday Meal Scheme in public secondary schools in Delta State.
3. There is no significant correlation between increased school enrollment and the Midday Meal Scheme in public secondary schools in Delta State.

This study aims to generate empirical insights into the factors affecting the utilization of the Midday Meal Scheme in Delta State. The findings will support policymakers in enhancing program execution, ensuring effective targeting of beneficiaries, and addressing barriers that limit student participation. Additionally, the study will contribute to the body of literature on school feeding programs in Nigeria, providing valuable perspectives on optimizing such initiatives to better address students' nutritional needs

Methodology

This study utilized a descriptive survey research design to explore the factors influencing the utilization of the Midday Meal Scheme in public secondary schools in Delta State. A total of 300 students were purposively selected from ten (10) randomly chosen public secondary schools in Ethiope West Local Government Area, as they are the primary beneficiaries whose perspectives provide critical insights into the scheme's effectiveness. The selection process was guided by specific inclusion criteria (students enrolled in public schools, active participants in the scheme, and those willing to provide consent) and exclusion criteria (students from private schools, non-participants, and those unwilling to take part). Data were collected using a self-developed, close-ended questionnaire based on a modified four-point Likert scale, with reliability assessed through Cronbach's Alpha, yielding a coefficient of 0.68. The study adhered to ethical guidelines, including obtaining informed consent, ensuring confidentiality, maintaining voluntary participation, and securing approval from school authorities and the Delta State Ministry of Education.

Results, Findings and Discussion

Objective 1: Impact of the Midday Meal Scheme on the poverty level of students in public secondary schools

Table 1: Distribution of students according to impact of the Midday Meal Scheme on the poverty level of students in public secondary schools

Variable	Mean	St. Dev
Daily Food Consumption Before MMS (No. of Meals)	1.8	0.7
Daily Food Consumption After MMS (No. of Meals)	2.9	0.5
Percentage of Students with Improved Nutritional Status (%)	75.3	10.5
Percentage of Students Attending School Regularly (%)	82.6	8.9
Academic Performance (Average Test Score /100) Before MMS	54.2	11.3
Academic Performance (Average Test Score /100) After MMS	68.7	9.8
Percentage of Students with Reduced Dropout Rates (%)	71.5	9.7

Source: Field survey, 2024

The findings in Table 1 provide clear evidence of the positive impact of the Midday Meal Scheme (MMS) on the poverty level of students in public secondary schools. The result showed that the program significantly improves nutritional intake, school attendance, and academic performance, while also reducing dropout rates.

Objective 2: Extent of State Government involvement in the implementation of the Midday Meal Scheme in public secondary schools

Table 2: Extent of State Government involvement in the implementation of the Midday Meal Scheme in public secondary schools

Variable	Mean	St. Dev
Number of Days Midday Meal Provided per Week	4.2	0.9
Government Funding Adequacy (1 = Low, 5 = High)	3.7	1.2
Availability of Nutritious Meals (1 = Poor, 5 = Excellent)	4.1	1
Percentage of Students Benefiting (%)	82.5	10.4
Reduction in Student Hunger Levels (1 = Low, 5 = High)	4.3	1.1
Perceived Improvement in Academic Performance (1 = Low, 5 = High)	3.9	1.3
Parents' Satisfaction with the Scheme (1 = Low, 5 = High)	4	1.1
Reduction in Household Food Expenses (₦)	8500	2300
Perceived Poverty Reduction among Beneficiaries (%)	70.4	14.6

Source: Field survey, 2024

The result from Table 2 show that Government involvement is reflected in funding adequacy, meal availability, and the number of meals provided per week. Student impact is measured by attendance rates, dropout reduction, and improved academic performance. A high mean score in key variables (e.g., 4.3 for

hunger reduction and 70.4% for poverty reduction) suggests that the Midday Meal Scheme contributes significantly to alleviating poverty.

Objective 3: Effect of the Midday Meal Scheme on school enrollment rates in public secondary schools

The descriptive statistics presented in the table provide key insights into the effectiveness of the Midday Meal Scheme on school enrollment rates and poverty alleviation among students in public secondary schools.

Table 3: Distribution of students according to effect of the Midday Meal Scheme on school enrollment rates in public secondary schools

Variable	Mean	St. Dev
School Enrollment Before Scheme (%)	65.3	12.3
School Enrollment After Scheme (%)	87.5	10.2
Average Attendance Rate (%)	82.1	8.5
Dropout Rate Before Scheme (%)	18.7	5.4
Dropout Rate After Scheme (%)	6.3	3.2
Number of Meals per Student (per week)	5.9	1.1
% of Students from Low-Income Families	73.2	14.6
% of Students Reporting Improved Nutrition	80.4	11.9
% of Parents Who Believe Scheme Helped Financially	78.5	9.7

Source: Field survey, 2024

The Midday Meal Scheme significantly increased school enrollment (by 22.2%), improved attendance (82.1%), reduced dropout rates (from 18.7% to 6.3%), enhanced student nutrition (80.4% reported improvement), and alleviated financial burdens on low-income families (78.5% of parents acknowledged economic relief), demonstrating its effectiveness in promoting education and reducing poverty.

Hypothesis 1 (H01): There would be no significant difference between poverty level of students and midday meal scheme in public secondary schools in Delta State.

Table 4: Summary of Chi-square analysis on Poverty Level of Students and Midday Meal Scheme.

Variable	Responses	Frequency	%	X ²	Df	Remark
Poverty Level	Disagree	110	36.67	82.00	1	Rejected
	Agree	190	63.33			
	TOTAL	300	100			

$\chi^2 = 82, df = 1 P > 0.05$. Critical value = 3.84.

Table 4 showed that 110 (36.67%) of the respondents disagree that the poverty level of students is not significance to midday meal scheme while 190 (53.33%) agree. The results showed that the computed Chi-square value of 82.00 is greater than the table (critical) value of 3.84 at 0.05 significance. Hypothesis 1 is therefore rejected which implies that the Midday Meal Scheme had a significant impact on reducing student poverty levels ($\chi^2 = 82, df = 1, p < 0.05$), indicating a strong association between the scheme and poverty reduction, as 63.33% of respondents agreed that it alleviated financial hardship by improving food security, increasing school participation, and reducing household expenses. The Midday Meal Scheme (MDM) significantly reduced poverty levels among students by alleviating food insecurity, reducing household financial burdens, and increasing school enrollment and attendance rates. The chi-square analysis ($\chi^2 = 82, p < 0.05$) confirms a strong association between the scheme and poverty reduction, as 63.33% of respondents

acknowledged its positive financial impact. This is in line with Paul et al. (2021) who reported that MDM had positive impact on students.

Hypothesis 2 (H0₂): There would be no significant difference between State Government's involvement and Midday Meal (MDM) scheme in public secondary schools in Delta State.

Table 5: Chi-square analysis on government's involvement and Midday meal scheme in public schools

Variable	Responses	Frequency	%	x ²	Df	Remark
Government Involvement (fund)	High involvement	125	41.67	62.50	1	Rejected
	Low involvement	175	58.33			
	TOTAL	300	100			

$x^2 = 62.50$, $df = 1$, $P > 0.05$, critical value 3.84.

Result in table 5 showed that 175 (58.33%) of the respondents disagree that government does not have full involvement in fund provision of the public schools midday meal scheme in Delta State. The government makes policies to guide the operations of schools of different levels. Even if the policies are made but not funded, the scheme will not be in operation. The remaining 125(41.67%) agree that government is involved in the midday meal scheme. These results showed that the computed x^2 value of 62.50 is greater than the table (critical) value of 3.84 at 0.05 significance. Hypothesis two is therefore rejected. This view was supported by Mordi (2010), who stated that it is not only the availability of food and the money to buy it alone but other factors as socio-economic factors, family size and political factors.

Hypothesis 3 (H0₃): There would be no significant difference between increase in school enrollment and Midday meal scheme in public schools in Delta State

Table 6: Summary of Chi-square analysis on increase in school Midday meal scheme.

Variable	Responses	Frequency	%	x ²	Df	Remark
Increase in School enrollment	Disagree	95	31.67	110.5	1	Rejected
	Agree	205	62.33			
	TOTAL					

$x^2 = 110.5$, $df = 1$, $P > 0.05$, critical value 3.84.

Table 6 showed that out of three hundred (300) respondents, 205 (62.33%) agree, 95 (31.67%) disagree. The percentage of total respondents that agree was 62.33% and greater than those who disagree (31.67%). Similarly, since the calculated value of 110.50 is greater than the critical (table) value of 3.84, the null hypothesis which states that there would be no significant between increase in school enrollment and midday meal scheme in public schools in Delta State is significant and therefore is rejected. This claim was supported by Mirakjar and Narayanswamy (2019) who stated that enrollment of public post primary schools in Delta was at increase. This increase was attributed to the encouragement of girl-child education and quest from people to acquire education for better living in the society.

Conclusion

The midday meal scheme at school is one of the essentials in the lives of school children. It serves as refreshment. By reason of this research, it has been found that the poverty level of the students' parents, state

government's non-involvement and increase in students' enrollment from the responses of the respondents showed that they affect the implementation of midday meal scheme in public secondary schools in Delta State. Observations revealed that there is no functioning midday meal in any of the public secondary schools except the Government Model High Schools in the State. In this study, all the independent variables examined significantly served as correlate of the use of midday meal scheme in public secondary schools in Delta State, with increase in students' enrollments contributing the highest. The implication of this is that students, parents and governments should adopt school-nutrition-friendly behaviours in order to prevent pangs of hunger and diseases among the students.

Recommendations

Based on these findings, the following recommendations are preferred:

1. The government and policymakers should strengthen and expand the Midday Meal Scheme to further alleviate student poverty, enhance food security, and improve school enrollment and attendance rates, ensuring its sustainability and effectiveness in addressing financial hardships among students.
2. Financial commitment and policy implementation for the Midday Meal Scheme should be targeted to ensure its sustainability and effectiveness in improving student welfare, as lack of full funding could hinder its impact despite well-intended policies.
3. The significant relationship between the Midday Meal Scheme and increased school enrollment in public schools in Delta State highlights the need for sustained and well-funded meal programs to further enhance student participation and educational access, particularly for marginalized groups.

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